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COMPETITIVE INTELLIGENCE IN INDIA IN GLOBAL SCENARIO

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ABSTRACT

Objective- *Broadly speaking, the term 'globalization' means integration of economies and societies through cross country flows of information, ideas, technologies, goods, services, capital, finance and people. Cross border integration can have several dimensions – cultural, social, political and economic. Nothing is an unmixed blessing. Globalization in its present form though spurred by far reaching technological changes is not a pure technological phenomenon. It has many dimensions including ideological. To deal with this phenomenon, we must understand the gains and losses, the benefits as well as dangers. To be forewarned, as the saying goes, is to be forearmed. But we should not throw the baby with bath water. . Competitive intelligence is more than analyzing competitors — it is about making the organization more competitive relative to its entire environment and stakeholders: customers, competitors, distributors, technologies, macro-economic data etc. The objective of this paper is to present the Competitive Intelligence in India in Global perspective since this concept is very important in the present scenario.*

Design / Methodology/ Approach- *The present research paper is conceptualized and is based on secondary data collected from various resources like books, news papers, management journals and internet. In order to have a practical experience, this paper has also analyzed successful implementation of Competitive Intelligence In India In Global perspective*

Findings- *Competitive Intelligence's real value is to provide managers with the organizational tool to learn what the competitor will do, not what the competitor has already done. the intelligence product is unlikely to be created from perfect input. We cannot truly and accurately predict the future until events have already taken place and it's too late. The firm finds itself in a position where it can only react to the competitor's move; it has lost the advantage it might have had if the right intelligence had been available earlier.*

Limitations- *Present research is conceptualized and based on secondary data; research could have been more authenticated if it would have been based on primary data.*

Practical implications- *Using these results, competitive intelligence departments and professionals can improve efficacy within their approach and execution strategies.*

Originality/Value- *The contribution of this paper is two-fold. It reveals many of the “state-of-the-art” levels of practice within current competitive intelligence efforts, and it proposes a model of the intelligence process.*

Key words: *Cross border integration, capitalist process, economic flows, economic restrictions, tariff and non-tariff barriers, CI tools.*

1. Introduction: Meaning of Competitive Intelligence and Globalization

1.1. Competitive Intelligence

A broad definition of **competitive intelligence** is the action of defining, gathering, analyzing, and distributing intelligence about products, customers, competitors and any aspect of the environment needed to support executives and managers in making strategic decisions for an organization.

Key points of this definition:

1. Competitive intelligence is an ethical and legal business practice, as opposed to industrial espionage which is illegal.
2. The focus is on the external business environment.
3. There is a process involved in gathering information, converting it into intelligence and then utilizing this in business decision making. CI professionals erroneously emphasize that if the intelligence gathered is not usable (or actionable) then it is not intelligence.

A more focused definition of CI regards it as the organizational function responsible for the early identification of risks and opportunities in the market before they become *obvious*. Experts also call this process the early signal analysis. This definition focuses attention on the difference between dissemination of widely available factual information (such as market statistics, financial reports, newspaper clippings) performed by functions such as libraries and information centers, and competitive intelligence which is a *perspective* on developments and events aimed at yielding a competitive edge.

The term CI is often viewed as synonymous with competitor analysis, but competitive intelligence is more than analyzing competitors — it is about making the organization more competitive relative to its entire environment and stakeholders: customers, competitors, distributors, technologies, macro-economic data etc.

Fig:1 Complete Competitive Intelligence

Source:<http://www.clearci.com/ci-software/competitive-intelligence-software-product-tour.html>

In the age of globalisation, no business is an island. For success, the business will need to deal with customers, suppliers, employees, and others. In the age of globalisation, in almost all cases there will also be other organizations offering similar products to similar customers. In the free economy, these other organizations are competitors. And their objective is the same - to grow, make money and succeed. Effectively, the businesses are at war - fighting to gain the same resource and territory: the customer. And like in war, it is necessary to understand the enemy:

- how he thinks;
- what his strengths are;
- what his weaknesses are;
- where he is vulnerable;
- where he can be attacked;
- where the risk of attack is too great....

and so on. And like in war, the competitor will have secrets that can be the difference between profit and loss, expansion or bankruptcy for the business. Identifying these secrets is thus crucial for business survival.

The rapid globalization of the markets has placed an even higher premium on effective business and competitive analysis. Improvements in communication technologies facilitate the opportunity to gather and verify the collected data.

If the management of a corporation is aware of its accurate competitive position it can formulate a business strategy that will optimized market penetration and customer retention. In today's global business environment, there is a cut throat race for every market share. The corporations which do not closely monitor their competitors are susceptible to not only losing their market share, but are also in danger of quickly becoming non-competitive. Being unaware of new strategies employed by your competitors can be fatal. Setting your own strategies means you first need to know those of your competitors to enable you to have a competitive edge. Intelligence is information that has been analyzed for decision making. It is important to understand the difference between information and intelligence. Information is the starting point; it is readily available numbers, statistics, bits of data about people, companies, products, and strategies. As a matter of fact, information overload is one of the leading problems of today's executive and the top reason for needing a competitive intelligence expert. Information becomes intelligence when is it distilled and analyzed. Combining this idea with those of competition or competitors leads to the concept of gathering and analyzing information about competitors for use in making management decisions. Competitive intelligence provides a link between information and business strategies and decisions. It is the process of turning vast quantities of information into action.

Examples of competitive intelligence include stock traders who analyze the data on prices and price movements to determine the best investments. These stock traders have the same data as other traders, but analysis of the data separates them from others. Another example is the Japanese automobile industry's analysis of the U.S.-automobile market in the 1970s. High gasoline prices and smaller families created a demand in the United States for smaller, more fuel-efficient cars. Japanese automakers employed competitive intelligence methods to determine this trend and then made manufacturing decisions based on it, beating the U.S. Big Three to market with high quality, fuel-efficient cars. Another example of successful use of competitive intelligence is AT&T's database of in-company experts. Part of this service is the

monitoring of companies with which their own employees are most interested. This led to some early insights of emerging competitors. A final example is how Wal-Mart stores studied problems Sears had with distribution, and built a state-of-the art distribution system so that Wal-Mart customers were not frustrated by out-of-stock items, as were Sears's customers.

1.2. Globalization

Broadly speaking, the term 'globalization' means integration of economies and societies through cross country flows of information, ideas, technologies, goods, services, capital, finance and people. Cross border integration can have several dimensions – cultural, social, political and economic. In fact, some people fear cultural and social integration even more than economic integration. The fear of “cultural hegemony” haunts many. Limiting ourselves to economic integration, one can see this happen through the three channels of (a) trade in goods and services, (b) movement of capital and (c) flow of finance. Besides, there is also the channel through movement of people.

Globalization is a capitalist process that has taken off as a concept in the wake of the collapse of communism as a viable alternate form of economic organisation as we are increasingly been seen as living in the era of globalisation. Globalisation describes the increased mobility of goods, services, labour, technology and finance & capital throughout the world. Although globalisation is not a new development, its pace has increased with the advent of new technologies, especially in the area of telecommunications. **Examples** of how globalisation effects Britain is in the current trend of UK business employing indian call centres for support & sales services, or for a clothing manufacturers to design its products in the UK, and make them in south-east Asia and then to sell them in north America.

The earliest concepts and predictions of globalization were penned by an **American entrepreneur-turned-minister Charles Taze Russell** who first coined the term '*corporate giants*' in 1897. Various social scientists have tried to demonstrate continuity between contemporary trends of globalization and earlier periods. The first era of globalization (in the fullest sense) during the 19th century was the rapid growth of international trade between the European imperial powers, the European colonies, and the United States. After World War II, globalization was restarted and was driven by major advances in technology, which led to lower trading costs. Globalization in the era since World War II was first the result of planning by economists, business interests, and politicians who recognized the costs

associated with protectionism and declining international economic integration. Their work led to the Bretton Woods conference and the founding of several international institutions intended to oversee the renewed processes of globalization, promoting growth and managing adverse consequences. These were the **International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (the World Bank)** and the International Monetary Fund. It has been facilitated by advances in technology which have reduced the costs of trade, and trade negotiation rounds, originally under the auspices of GATT, which led to a series of agreements to remove restrictions on free trade. The Uruguay round (1984 to 1995) led to a treaty to create the World Trade Organization (WTO), to mediate trade disputes and set up a uniform platform of trading. Other bi- and multilateral trade agreements, including sections of Europe's Maastricht Treaty and the **North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA)** have also been signed in pursuit of the goal of reducing tariffs and barriers to trade. Looking specifically at economic globalization, it can be measured in different ways. These centre around the four main economic flows that characterize globalization: Goods and services, e.g. exports plus imports as a proportion of national income or per capita of population Labour/people, e.g. net migration rates; inward or outward migration flows, weighted by population Capital, e.g. inward or outward direct investment as a proportion of national income or per head of population Technology, e.g. international research & development flows; proportion of populations (and rates of change thereof) using particular inventions (especially 'factor-neutral' technological advances such as the telephone, motorcar, broadband)

To what extent a nation-state or culture is globalised in a particular year has until most recently been measured employing simple proxies like flows of trade, migration, or foreign direct investment, as described above.

1.3. Historical Development of Competitive Intelligent:

As globalization is not only an economic phenomenon, a multivariate approach to measuring globalization is the recent index calculated by the Swiss Think tank KOF. The index measures the three main dimensions of globalization: economic, social, and political. In addition to three indices measuring these dimensions, an overall index of globalization and sub-indices referring to actual economic flows, economic restrictions, data on personal contact, data on information flows, and data on cultural proximity is calculated. Data are available on a yearly basis for 122 countries. According to the index, the world's most

globalised country is Belgium, followed by Austria, Sweden, the United Kingdom and the Netherlands. The least globalised countries according to the KOF-index are Haiti, Myanmar the Central African Republic and Burundi. Other measures conceptualize Globalization as Diffusion and develop interactive procedure to capture the degree of its impact Jahn 2006. The literature associated with the field of competitive intelligence is best exemplified by the detailed bibliographies that were published in the Society of Competitive Intelligence Professionals refereed academic journal called The Journal of Competitive Intelligence and Management. Although elements of organizational intelligence collection have been a part of business for many years, the history of competitive intelligence arguably began in the U.S. in the 1970s, although the literature on the field pre-dates this time by at least several decades. In 1980, Michael Porter published the study *Competitive-Strategy: Techniques for Analyzing Industries and Competitors* which is widely viewed as the foundation of modern competitive intelligence. This has since been extended most notably by the pair of Craig Fleisher and Babette Bensoussan, who through several popular books on competitive analysis have added 48 commonly applied competitive intelligence analysis techniques to the practitioner's tool box. In 1985, Leonard Fuld published his best selling book dedicated to competitor intelligence. However, the institutionalization of CI as a formal activity among American corporations can be traced to 1988, when Ben and Tamar Gilad published the first organizational model of a formal corporate CI function, which was then adopted widely by US companies. The first professional certification program (CIP) was created in 1996 with the establishment of The Fuld-Gilad-Herring Academy of Competitive Intelligence in Cambridge, MA, followed in 2004 by the Institute for Competitive Intelligence.

In 1986 the *Society of Competitive Intelligence Professionals* (SCIP) was founded in the U.S. and grew in the late 1990s to around 6000 members worldwide, mainly in the U.S. and Canada, but with large numbers especially in UK and Germany. Due to financial difficulties in 2009, the organization merged with Frost & Sullivan under the Frost & Sullivan Institute. SCIP has since been renamed "Strategic & Competitive Intelligence Professionals" to emphasise the strategic nature of the subject, and also to refocus the organisation's general approach, while keeping the existing SCIP brandname and logo. A number of efforts have been made to discuss the field's advances in post-secondary (university) education, covered by several authors including Blenkhorn & Fleisher, Fleisher, Fuld, Prescott, and McGonagle, among others. Although the general view would be that competitive intelligence concepts can be readily found and taught in many business schools around the globe, there

are still relatively few dedicated academic programs, majors, or degrees in the field, a concern to academics in the field who would like to see it further researched. These issues were widely discussed by over a dozen knowledgeable individuals in a special edition of the Competitive Intelligence Magazine that was dedicated to this topic. In France, a Specialized Master in Economic Intelligence and Knowledge Management was created in 1995 within the CERAM Business School, now SKEMA Business School in Paris, with the objective of delivering a full and professional training in Economic Intelligence. A Centre for Global Intelligence and Influence was created in September 2011 in the same School.

On the other hand, practitioners and companies regard professional accreditation as especially important in this field. In 2011, SCIP recognized the Fuld-Gilad-Herring Academy of Competitive Intelligence's CIP certification process as its global, dual-level (CIP-I and CIP-II) certification program.

1.4. Some Saying about Competitive Intelligence

Around the year 500 BC, the great Chinese military strategist, **Sun Tzu** wrote a treatise on the **Art of War**. From a 21st century perspective, many of Sun Tzu's approaches would be viewed as barbaric today. Apart from that, his views on strategy are still relevant today - for both Military Personnel and business leaders looking at how to win against competitors. For instance:

- “1.If you are ignorant of both your enemy and yourself,
then you are a fool and certain to be defeated in every battle.
2. If you know yourself, but not your enemy,
for every battle won, you will suffer a loss.
3. If you know your enemy and yourself, you will win every battle.”

Business competitors are other organizations offering services and selling their products.

Through knowing our **Competitors** we may be able to

“predict their next moves,
exploit their weaknesses
and undermine their strengths.”

Customers usually know the differences between companies - their good points and bad points. They know that **company A** is cheaper than **company B** and that **company C** has a better after-sales service. For a business to operate in a market and not know the same, and more, is tantamount to giving up the battle without even starting. As Frederick the Great said:

“It is pardonable to be defeated, but never to be surprised”

- the **same** product or service now.
- Other organizations offering **similar** products or services now.
- Organizations that could offer the **same or similar** products or services in the future.
- Organizations that could **remove the need** for a product or service.

So what is involved?:

There are four stages in monitoring competitors - **the four Cs**: are

- **Collecting the information** (with a first stage - deciding what to collect)
- **Converting information into intelligence** (*with three steps: CIA -Collate and catalogue it, Integrate it with other pieces of information and Analyse and interpret it*)
- **Communicating the intelligence.**
- **Countering any adverse competitor actions** - i.e. using the intelligence.

One mistake a lot of people make is to start by collecting information without thinking how the information will be used. There is no value in information that will just sit on a shelf. If it cannot be used to inform the business's strategic or tactical decisions then the time, money, and effort spent collecting it is wasted.

- The business may be planning a new product - so information on what competitors are doing in the same area will help in the decision processes and plans for this new product.
- Alternatively, the business may be looking at how the industry will develop over the next 5 or 10 years.
- Or perhaps the board is looking at a potential merger, acquisition or business partnership.

The information requirements for each of these business decisions will be completely different and so the information that should be sought will also be different.

Thus before starting to search for information the competitor analyst needs to sit back and define what they are looking for and why. They need to identify the key areas of concern for the business decision makers requesting the information, and aim to satisfy these.

2. Review of Literature

Competitive intelligence is a process consisting of phases that are linked (**Nasri 2011**). The output of each phase is the input to the next phase (**Bartes 2012**). The overall output of the CI process is an input to the decision-making process (**Wright et al. 2009**). Most CI definitions clearly reveal that it is a process that produces actionable intelligence (Brody 2008). According to **Du Toit and Muller (2004)**, without a proper intelligence process and structure, it is difficult to develop intelligence. Also, without the visible support of and utilisation of intelligence by top management, the process will be flawed (**Nasri 2011**). Put differently, the overriding influence on successful CI process is the existence of a management support, culture and structure that encourages and develops CI activities in companies (**Nasri 2011**). Therefore, management must plan, support and implement a CI process. Given the confusion in the field of CI on how the CI process should be structured, some agreement within the CI field on this should be reached (**Wright & Calof 2006**). A study conducted by **Carr (2003)** discovered that CI experts describe the CI process as a cycle, as a linear process, using fourpoint models, as a scientific method and as a pyramid. Some scholars outline many phases in the CI process, whilst others identify fewer phases. Some scholars name the same phases differently, thereby adding to the confusion in the field of CI. The following CI process models were established in the literature. According to **Calof (1998)**, the CI process is made up of obtaining a CI request, collecting information, analysing and synthesising information, communicating intelligence, and managing the CI process. This CI process model does not incorporate the capturing and storing of collected information. **Calof and Skinner (1998)** view the CI process as a cycle made up of four phases: planning and direction, data collection, information analysis and intelligence dissemination. These two scholars term the information collection phase ‘data collection’ and omit information capturing and storing. Their CI process model does not incorporate influential factors such as decision-makers, feedback, organisational awareness and culture, and process and structure. **Kahaner (1998)** also defines CI as a cycle process with four

phases: planning and direction, data and information collection, analysis and dissemination of intelligence to those who will use it. This CI process model omits information capturing and storage and terms the information collection phase 'data and information collection' phase. Information consists of organised data. Therefore, in information there is data; there is no need to use both terms together in the name of this phase. Melo and Medeiros (2007) add evaluation to **Kahaner's (1998)** CI process cycle to make it a five-phase cycle composed of planning, collection, analysis, dissemination and evaluation. These scholars also omitted information capturing and storage and the influential factors. **Cruywagen (2002)** views the CI process as a cycle with a number of distinguishable phases, including planning and direction, collection, evaluation, analysis and dissemination.

Although **Cruywagen (2002)** incorporated feedback, the other influential factors such as decision-makers, organisational awareness and culture and process and structure are omitted. The information capturing and storage phase is also omitted. **Dishman and Calof (2002)** establish six phases of the CI process: planning and focus, collection, analysis, communication, process or structure and organisational awareness and culture. Although this is an improved CI process model, it omits information capturing and storage and feedback. According to **Viviers, Saayman and Muller (2005)**, the CI process is a cycle made up of planning and focus; collection; analysis; communication; and awareness, culture, process and structure. This CI process model also omits information capturing and storage and feedback. **Botha and Boon (2008)** view the CI process as a cycle consisting of seven phases: intelligence needs and determining key intelligence topics; planning and direction; collection; information processing; analysis; dissemination; and intelligence users and decision-makers. This model incorporates influential factors as phases and omits feedback. However, unlike other scholars, they recognise the need to capture and store collected information. **Wright and Calof (2006)** identify four phases of the CI process: planning or focus, collection, analysis and communication. They also indicate that process, structure, culture, awareness and attitude are undeniable influences of CI process success. Their CI process model omits information capturing and storage, decision-makers and feedback. According to **SCIP (2007)**, CI is a cycle with five phases: planning and direction, collection activities, analysis, dissemination and feedback. This CI process model omits information capturing and storage and other influential factors such as decision-makers, organisational awareness and culture, and process and structure. **Bose (2008)** views the CI process as a cycle made up of planning and direction, collection, analysis, dissemination and feedback. This CI process model omits

information capturing and storage and other influential factors such as decision-makers, organisational awareness and culture and process and structure. According to **Sawka and Hohhof (2008)**, the CI process is a cycle made up of the following interrelated phases: planning and direction, collection, analysis and production and dissemination. These scholars term the information analysis phase ‘analysis and production’. This means that intelligence is produced in the analysing phase. Their CI process model omits information capturing and storage and all the influential factors previously mentioned. According to **Cucui (2009)**, CI is a process consisting of the following steps: monitoring business environment, gathering, analysing and filtering and disseminating intelligence. This model differs from the rest of the scholars’ models because of the phase names. The planning and direction phase is called ‘monitoring business environment’. The information collection phase is called ‘gathering’ and the intelligence dissemination phase is called ‘filtering and dissemination’. This CI process model also omits information capturing and storage and other influential factors mentioned. Competitive intelligence, according to **Shi, Mou and Wan (2009)**, is a cycle process made up of defining CI demand, gathering information, processing information and providing final services to meet the demand. Just like **Cucui (2009)**, **Shi et al. (2009)** name their CI process phases differently. They omit information capturing and storage and all the influential factors. According to **Haddadi, Dousset and Berrada (2010)**, CI is a cycle process made up of understanding the need, researching and gathering information, processing information and disseminating information. These scholars use different phase names and omit information capturing and storage. They also omit all the influential factors and call the information analysis phase ‘processing information’. **Muller (2002)** identifies six phases in the CI process: planning and focus; collection; analysis; communication; process and structure and organisational awareness and culture. **Strauss and Du Toit (2010)** propose a seventh phase: ‘skills development’. According to them, training clears up misconceptions regarding CI, improves communication, encourages easy transfer of expertise and skills and fosters a mindset of awareness within the enterprise. They conclude that the CI process is not complete without skills development. Their CI process model omits information capturing and storage and feedback. The CI process, according to **McGonagle and Vella (2012)**, is divided into five phases, each linked to the other by a feedback loop. These phases are: establishing the CI needs, collecting the raw data, evaluating and analysing the raw data, communicating the finished intelligence and taking action. Unlike most scholars, **McGonagle and Vella’s (2012)** CI process model emphasises collection and analysis of data rather than information. Their model introduces the taking action phase, in which decision makers make

decisions. They omit other influential factors such as organisational awareness and culture and process and structure.

There is no work on Competitive Intelligence in India in Global perspective so this is the research gap. The objective of this paper is to present the Competitive Intelligence in India in Global perspective since this concept is very important in the present scenario.

3. Objectives of this Study

The following are objectives of this study:

- i) To find out the drivers of Competitive Intelligence Drivers in India
- ii) To find out Competitive Intelligence Tools in India
- iii) The Process of Competitive Intelligent in India
- iv) Major Areas of Competitive intelligence In India

4. Methodology

The secondary data have been used in preparing this paper. The sources of data are: Journals, website, Text Books, Reference Books, Government Publications, Unpublished Thesis, etc

5. Drivers of competitive intelligence in India

While the practice of competitive intelligence is as old as competition and private enterprise itself, it has emerged as a systematic discipline and a profession in the developed economies only in the last 30 years or so. In India its practice is relatively new, but expected to grow very rapidly.

There are several reasons that come to my mind, why competitive intelligence is gaining appeal in corporate India.

During the license raj, businesses concentrated on gaining access to the scarce permits and licenses that enabled them to be in business and grow. Once they had the required permits, they faced little competition. The economy was also insulated from the rest of the world with limited movement of goods and services across borders.

Liberalisation of economic policies in the 1990s, brought in the first winds of competition for businesses in India, from domestic new entrants as well as foreign companies. But this remained limited, as both businesses and regulators struggled to find their feet in the new environment. Entry of foreign companies was also slow, as they cautiously gauged the Indian market.

By mid 2000s, however, the business environment had decidedly changed. GDP growth gained momentum and led to a cycle of further growth in both capital investment as well as consumption expenditure. Also, multinationals started looking at India as an attractive market when the recession hit most of the developed world in 2008-09. The emerging markets including India are drawing the multinationals even more now, as recovery in the developed countries is proving slow and painful.

This has brought in another gust of competition in India. As the multinationals are struggling in the developed markets, they are looking at possible opportunities in the emerging markets with renewed vigour. Companies in India need better competitive intelligence if they want to survive this onslaught of global attention.

In addition to competition, multinationals are bringing in a cultural change in corporate India. They are bringing in **global management practices**, which will very soon become the benchmark for Indian companies as well. Already, one can see instances of family run businesses bringing in more professional management in order to bring in a global perspective in their businesses. Further, the age old reliance on intuition to make decisions is proving inadequate. Intuition is guided by previous experience; so it works well in a stable and predictable environment, not the dynamic one that we now operate in. Competitive intelligence and the culture of backing all decisions with hard data and analysis is also permeating into the Indian boardrooms, thanks to the changing business culture.

Another key driver of competitive intelligence in India is the increased availability of tools and techniques for doing competitive intelligence. Fragmentation in Indian industries, the large unorganized sector, and under-documentation mean that data availability in India is very low. The degree of difficulty in doing competitive intelligence is therefore much harder. However, CI professionals in India are innovating methodologies and techniques to overcome this problem. Also, increased digitization of information has meant that more information is now available from secondary sources than before. Technology is also coming up with

solutions for cutting through the noise on the Internet and getting to reliable and usable information faster.

6. Competitive Intelligence Tools in India:

Here's a list of 11 tools that can help you track our competitors movements on the Web and give us actionable information that we can use. It doesn't make us a bad person. It makes us a savvy site owner. These tools are as follows:

i) Google Alerts

Google Alerts are great little inventions because they allow you track virtually anything and have it delivered either to your email or RSS. What kinds of stuff should you be tracking? The name of our competitor's company, their employee names, their CEO, product names, locations, mentions of new features, etc. What kinds of media are you looking for? Their blogs, social profiles, photos, videos, Flickr accounts, Face book pages, etc. Why? The more you know, the better off you are to make smart decisions.

ii) Twitter

Follow your competitors on Twitter. Follow their employees. Follow the people that engage most often with your competitors. Follow the people your competitors are following. Using Private Twitter Lists to do it all discretely. Private Lists are a goldmine for stalking. I mean, researching.

iii) Twitter Search

Create RSS feeds or Save Twitter Searches to track important keywords, competitors' Twitter user names, and product names (yours and theirs). You can also use the Advanced Geo search to key in a certain radius from your competitor's storefront.

iv) Bit.ly

If you're using Twitter, you're probably already familiar with bit.ly. It's one of the many URL shortening services out there. What's different about bit.ly is that it gives you really great link stat information. It will tell you how many people clicked on your link, how many times it was retweeted, how many people clicked on the retweeted link, what times of day people retweeted it, who was doing the actual retweeting, etc. It's a really great way to find and identify your network online so you can leverage them in the future.

v) Yahoo Site Explorer

Knowing that links are an essential part of getting your site to rank, Yahoo Site Explorer can show you WHO is linking to your competitors, as well as who's linking to you. Where are competitors getting their links from? How can you get links from similar sources? What holes do they have in their link profile that you can capitalize on? This tool will tell you.

vi) SEO for Firefox

This is great FF plugin offered by SEO Book's Aaron Wall that gives site owners a robust look at whatever site they're looking at. It tells you a site's PageRank, age, number of links at a certain domain/page, how it's done in social media, how many people are subscribed to its blog, if it's listed in DMOZ or the Yahoo Directory, etc. Because it offers such great information about links, many people like to use it evaluate competitor's content pieces.

vii) Quark base

Once you put your URL in it will tell you the most recent and the most popular pages from a certain site that have been submitted. You can see where they've been submitted, how many votes they received, how many subscribers they have, etc. You can also search by "submitted on" or "submitted by" to see where your competitors are having their content submitted and who's doing the submitting.

viii) Social Mention

This is a pretty neat tool. Enter in a search term (competitor's name, product name, keyword, etc) and SocialMention will track down what people are saying about that term across different blogs and social outlets. It will even attempt to track sentiment analysis to tell you if the mentions are positive, negative or neutral (this can get a bit wonky). It will tell you how many times a keyword was talked about, the time frame, and let you subscribe to an RSS feed for that term or export the information as a CSV. It's one of my personal favorite tools to play with.

ix) Compete

Compete will give you a complete profile of any site on the Web. You give them the domain and give you an approximation of their unique visitors and the keywords that are bringing people to their site. You can also compare several different sites up against each other. There's a paid option which will give you even more analytical type information, as well.

x) copernic.com

Copernic offers a great tracker tool that will look for new content on your competitors' Web pages and then email you a highlighted version so you know what they changed. If they put up a page about a new product they'll soon be carrying, you'll know. If they start altering text to rank for different keywords, you'll know. If they update their employee page to create new positions, you'll know. It's a \$49.95 investment but, I think it's worth it.

xi) Domaintools.com

Domaintools.com will collect a bunch of information about a Web site and report back. You can find out if your competitors are listed in the Yahoo directory, get registration details, what other sites are on the same IP (may be sites that company also owns), etc. You can also set up Registration Alerts to inform you each time your competitor creates a new domain name or a Mark Alert to tell you if they've used a particular keyword.

7. The Process of Competitive Intelligent In India

Today, competitive intelligence is an important activity within corporations, serving all areas of business functioning: research and development, human resources, sales, etc. A recent survey by The Futures Group found that 80 percent of large, U.S.-based organizations have a formal, in-house, competitive intelligence department. In the future, competitive intelligence activities will become standard. The wide availability of information on the Web makes competitive intelligence more accessible to medium-size and small firms. Software tools to analyze and disseminate intelligence also make it easier to implement competitive intelligence tools. The process of competitive intelligence is outlined in the following steps:

1. Setting intelligence objectives (i.e., designing the requirements)
2. Collecting and organizing data about the industry and competitors
3. Analyzing and interpreting the data
4. Information Transfer to the Customers
5. Disseminating the intelligence
6. This can be understood through this figure:1:

Fig. 2: CI process (source: Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development, Vol. 1 No. 2, December 2013 P.9)

8. Setting the Objectives

A clear statement of the intelligence needs of the organization should be outlined by management. If this step is ignored, the competitive intelligence department will be bogged down with too much information and possibly distracted by ad-hoc requests for data. This step is necessary regardless of where in the organization the competitive intelligence department is located. Some corporations have competitive intelligence report directly to the CEO; in others, it is located in marketing or in research and development. The role of any competitive intelligence program should be driven by the needs of the corporation, especially areas that have key performance consequences.

Competitive intelligence is not spying on the competition. It has been associated in the past with the political and military intelligence used during the Cold War era. Because of this association, many people think that competitive intelligence uses illegal, shady, or unethical means to gather information about competitors. Visions of wiretapping, bribing competitor's employees, or stealing information come to mind. This is not true today. Such techniques can

damage the reputation and image of corporations and are not worth the risk. SCIP takes a strong position on the importance of ethics and developed a code of ethics for members. Note the words, "legal and ethical," and the emphasis on retrieving data from "open sources." Competitive intelligence experts use openly-available information. They do dig into public records and government databases and use the latest technology (such as satellite photoreconnaissance and software tools such as spiders) to help gather and analyze large datasets. However, the professionals and companies for which they work do not use illegal methods.

9. Major Areas of Competitive Intelligence:

Competitive intelligence is usually composed of five major areas of endeavor, and is performed under three main approaches in the CI framework:

- Assessment of strategies
- Competitor perceptions
- Effectiveness of current operations
- Competitor capabilities
- Long-term market prospects

Strategic intelligence is concerned mainly with competitor analysis or gaining an understanding of a competitor's future goals, current strategy, assumptions held about itself and the industry, and capabilities -- diagnostic components. Intelligence about the firm's major customers, suppliers and partners (in marketing or research and development alliances) is often also of strategic value.

Tactical intelligence is generally operational and on a smaller-scale, not so centered on being predictive. Tactical issues include competitors' terms of sale, their price policies and the plans they have for changing the way in which they differentiate one or more of their products from yours. Middle-level marketing and sales managers number among some of the main users of tactical intelligence. They want to know how to win the day, today.

Counter intelligence is defending company secrets. Every firm has competitors as interested in knowing your plans as you are in knowing theirs, maybe even more so. Often, this area of

endeavor will involve security and information technology, but others are often overlooked, such as hiring and firing strategies, to contain competitor opportunities within the firm.

Competitive intelligence is the determination of solutions to these principle factors and determinants of ongoing competitive advantage:

- What is the basis of competition
- Where the firm competes
- Who does the competitor compete against
- How does the firm compete

10. **CI is focused on decision making**

Seldom do people realize that business, just like life is merely a series of decisions. And global firms have a growing need for the necessary information on which to base decisions concerning the conduct and development of each of their firm's strategic objectives, and the protection of their organizations against threats from their competitors.

11. **The Cycle of Competitive Intelligence**

The CIA describes the intelligence cycle as "the process by which raw information is acquired, gathered, transmitted, evaluated, analyzed and made available as finished intelligence for policymakers to use in decision-making and action." There are five steps which constitute this cycle:

- planning and direction
- collection and research
- processing and storage
- analysis and production
- dissemination and delivery

There are seven questions to be answered prior to making investment decisions in CI:

- what do we need to know?
- what do we already know?
- why do we need to know it?

- when do we need to know it?
- what will we do with the intelligence once we have it?
- what will it cost to get it?
- what could it cost not to get it?

12. CI's Final Product

The product of the intelligence cycle, is evaluated information. It is finished intelligence, packaged in a format appropriate as much to the intelligence itself, as it is to the customer for the intelligence, the decision-maker.

In practice, the intelligence product is unlikely to be created from perfect input. We cannot truly and accurately predict the future until events have already taken place and it's too late. The firm finds itself in a position where it can only react to the competitor's move; it has lost the advantage it might have had if the right intelligence had been available earlier. So, although we can't know for certain the minutiae associated with exact details, we can discover plans and roughly-hewn strategies.

CI's real value is to provide managers with the organizational tool to learn what the competitor will do, not what the competitor has already done.

Ethics and ethical behavior are concerns here and since the area is usually perceived as positive to a company's reputation and competitiveness, it would not be useful for a firm to undertake its intelligence activities without regard to ethical or legal considerations. Everything a firm needs to know about the competition can be obtained by legally available means. What are the bottom line benefits of CI? Improved market knowledge, improved cross-functional relationships in the organization, greater confidence in making strategic plans, and improvements in product quality versus the competition. In short, better business performance through doing things better.

13. Historical Development of Globalization:

Global developments have also been uneven in competitive intelligence. Several academic journals, particularly the Journal of Competitive Intelligence and Management in its third volume, provided coverage of the field's global development. For example, in 1997 the *Ecole de Guerre Economique (School of economic warfare)* was founded in Paris, France. It is the

first European institution which teaches the tactics of economic warfare within a globalizing world. In Germany, competitive intelligence was unattended until the early 1990s. The term "competitive intelligence" first appeared in German literature in 1997. In 1995 a German SCIP chapter was founded, which is now second in terms of members in Europe. In summer 2004 the Institute for Competitive Intelligence was founded, which provides a post-graduate certification program for Competitive Intelligence Professionals. Japan is currently the only country that officially maintains an economic intelligence agency (JETRO). It was founded by the Ministry of International Trade and Industry (MITI) in 1958.

Accepting the importance of competitive intelligence, major multinational corporations, such as ExxonMobil, Procter & Gamble, and Johnson and Johnson, have created formal CI units. Importantly, organizations execute competitive intelligence activities not only as a safeguard to protect against market threats and changes, but also as a method for finding new opportunities and trends.

Globalization has been a historical process with ebbs and flows. During the Pre-World War I period of 1870 to 1914, there was rapid integration of the economies in terms of trade flows, movement of capital and migration of people. The growth of globalization was mainly led by the technological forces in the fields of transport and communication. There were less barriers to flow of trade and people across the geographical boundaries. Indeed there were no passports and visa requirements and very few non-tariff barriers and restrictions on fund flows. The pace of globalization, however, decelerated between the First and the Second World War. The inter-war period witnessed the erection of various barriers to restrict free movement of goods and services. Most economies thought that they could thrive better under high protective walls. After World War II, all the leading countries resolved not to repeat the mistakes they had committed previously by opting for isolation. Although after 1945, there was a drive to increased integration; it took a long time to reach the Pre-World War I level. In terms of percentage of exports and imports to total output, the US could reach the pre-World War level of 11 per cent only around 1970. Most of the developing countries which gained Independence from the colonial rule in the immediate Post-World War II period followed an import substitution industrialization regime. The Soviet bloc countries were also shielded from the process of global economic integration. However, times have changed. In the last two decades, the process of globalization has proceeded with greater vigor. The former Soviet bloc countries are getting integrated with the global economy. More and more developing countries are turning towards outward oriented policy of growth. Yet, studies

point out that trade and capital markets are no more globalized today than they were at the end of the 19th century. Nevertheless, there are more concerns about globalization now than before because of the nature and speed of transformation. What is striking in the current episode is not only the rapid pace but also the enormous impact of new information technologies on market integration, efficiency and industrial organization. Globalization of financial markets has far outpaced the integration of product markets.

14. Gains from Globalization

The gains from globalization can be analyzed in the context of the three types of channels of economic globalization identified earlier.

14.1. Trade in Goods and Services

According to the standard theory, international trade leads to allocation of resources that is consistent with comparative advantage. This results in specialization which enhances productivity. It is accepted that international trade, in general, is beneficial and that restrictive trade practices impede growth. That is the reason why many of the emerging economies, which originally depended on a growth model of import substitution, have moved over to a policy of outward orientation. However, in relation to trade in goods and services, there is one major concern. Emerging economies will reap the benefits of international trade only if they reach the full potential of their resource availability. This will probably require time. That is why international trade agreements make exceptions by allowing longer time to developing economies in terms of reduction in tariff and non-tariff barriers. “Special and differentiated treatment”, as it is very often called has become an accepted principle.

14.2. Movement of Capital

Capital flows across countries have played an important role in enhancing the production base. This was very much true in 19th and 20th centuries. Capital mobility enables the total savings of the world to be distributed among countries which have the highest investment potential. Under these circumstances, one country’s growth is not constrained by its own domestic savings. The inflow of foreign capital has played a significant role in the development in the recent period of the East Asian countries. The current account deficit of some of these countries had exceeded 5 per cent of the GDP in most of the period when growth was rapid. Capital flows can take either the form of foreign direct investment or portfolio investment. For developing countries the preferred alternative is foreign direct investment. Portfolio investment does not directly lead to expansion of productive capacity.

It may do so, however, at one step removed. Portfolio investment can be volatile particularly in times of loss of confidence. That is why countries want to put restrictions on portfolio investment. However, in an open system such restrictions cannot work easily.

14.3. Financial Flows

The rapid development of the capital market has been one of the important features of the current process of globalization. While the growth in capital and foreign exchange markets have facilitated the transfer of resources across borders, the gross turnover in foreign exchange markets has been extremely large. It is estimated that the gross turnover is around \$ 1.5 trillion per day worldwide (Frankel, 2000). This is of the order of hundred times greater than the volume of trade in goods and services. Currency trade has become an end in itself. The expansion in foreign exchange markets and capital markets is a necessary pre-requisite for international transfer of capital. However, the volatility in the foreign exchange market and the ease with which funds can be withdrawn from countries have created often times panic situations. The most recent example of this was the East Asian crisis. Contagion of financial crises is a worrying phenomenon. When one country faces a crisis, it affects others. It is not as if financial crises are solely caused by foreign exchange traders. What the financial markets tend to do is to exaggerate weaknesses. Herd instinct is not uncommon in financial markets. When an economy becomes more open to capital and financial flows, there is even greater compulsion to ensure that factors relating to macro-economic stability are not ignored. This is a lesson all developing countries have to learn from East Asian crisis. As one commentator aptly said “The trigger was sentiment, but vulnerability was due to fundamentals”.

15. India’s Scene:

The economic changes initiated have had a dramatic effect on the overall growth of the economy. It also heralded the integration of the Indian economy into the global economy. The Indian economy was in major crisis in 1991 when foreign currency reserves went down to \$1 billion. Globalization had its impact on various sectors including Agricultural, Industrial, Financial, Health sector and many others. It was only after the LPG policy i.e. Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization launched by the then Finance Minister Man Mohan Singh that India saw its development in various sectors.

16. Advent of New Economic Policy

After suffering a huge financial and economic crisis Dr. Man Mohan Singh brought a new policy which is known as Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization Policy (LPG Policy) also known as New Economic Policy, 1991 as it was a measure to come out of the crisis that was going on at that time. The following measures were taken to liberalize and globalize the economy:

1. Devaluation: To solve the balance of payment problem Indian currency were devaluated by 18 to 19%.
2. Disinvestment: To make the LPG model smooth many of the public sectors were sold to the private sector.
3. Allowing Foreign Direct Investment (FDI): FDI was allowed in a wide range of sectors such as Insurance (26%), defense industries (26%) etc.
4. NRI Scheme: The facilities which were available to foreign investors were also given to NRIs.

The New Economic Policy (NEP-1991) introduced changes in the areas of trade policies, monetary & financial policies, fiscal & budgetary policies, and pricing & institutional reforms. The salient features of NEP-1991 are (i) liberalization (internal and external), (ii) extending privatization, (iii) redirecting scarce Public Sector Resources to Areas where the private sector is unlikely to enter, (iv) globalization of economy, and (v) market friendly state.

17. Consequences of Globalization:

The implications of globalization for a national economy are many. Globalization has intensified interdependence and competition between economies in the world market. This is reflected in Interdependence in regard to trading in goods and services and in movement of capital. As a result domestic economic developments are not determined entirely by domestic policies and market conditions. Rather, they are influenced by both domestic and international policies and economic conditions. It is thus clear that a globalizing economy, while formulating and evaluating its domestic policy cannot afford to ignore the possible actions and reactions of policies and developments in the rest of the world. This constrained the policy option available to the government which implies loss of policy autonomy to some extent, in decision-making at the national level.

Now for Further analysis we take up Impact of Globalization on various sector of Indian Economy.

17.1. Impact of Globalization on Agricultural Sector:

Agricultural Sector is the mainstay of the rural Indian economy around which socio-economic privileges and deprivations revolve and any change in its structure is likely to have a corresponding impact on the existing pattern of Social equity. The liberalization of India's economy was adopted by India in 1991. Facing a severe economic crisis, India approached the IMF for a loan, and the IMF granted what is called a 'structural adjustment' loan, which is a loan with certain conditions attached which relate to a structural change in the economy. Essentially, the reforms sought to gradually phase out government control of the market (liberalization), privatize public sector organizations (privatization), and reduce export subsidies and import barriers to enable free trade (globalization). Globalization has helped in:

- Raising living standards,
- Alleviating poverty,
- Assuring food security,
- Generating buoyant market for expansion of industry and services, and
- Making substantial contribution to the national economic growth.

17.2 Impact of Globalization on Industrial Sector:

Effects of Globalization on Indian Industry started when the government opened the country's markets to foreign investments in the early 1990s. Globalization of the Indian Industry took place in its various sectors such as steel, pharmaceutical, petroleum, chemical, textile, cement, retail, and BPO.

Globalization means the dismantling of trade barriers between nations and the integration of the nations economies through financial flow, trade in goods and services, and corporate investments between nations. Globalization has increased across the world in recent years due to the fast progress that has been made in the field of technology especially in communications and transport. The government of India made changes in its economic policy in 1991 by which it allowed direct foreign investments in the country. The benefits of the effects of globalization in the Indian Industry are that many foreign companies set up

industries in India, especially in the pharmaceutical, BPO, petroleum, manufacturing, and chemical sectors and this helped to provide employment to many people in the country. This helped reduce the level of unemployment and poverty in the country. Also the benefit of the Effects of Globalization on Indian Industry are that the foreign companies brought in highly advanced technology with them and this helped to make the Indian Industry more technologically advanced.

The negative Effects of Globalization on Indian Industry are that with the coming of technology the number of labor required decreased and this resulted in many people being removed from their jobs. This happened mainly in the pharmaceutical, chemical, manufacturing, and cement industries.

17.3. Impact on Financial Sector:

Reforms of the financial sector constitute the most important component of India's programme towards economic liberalization. The recent economic liberalization measures have opened the door to foreign competitors to enter into our domestic market. Innovation has become a must for survival. Financial intermediaries have come out of their traditional approach and they are ready to assume more credit risks. As a consequence, many innovations have taken place in the global financial sectors which have its own impact on the domestic sector also. The emergences of various financial institutions and regulatory bodies have transformed the financial services sector from being a conservative industry to a very dynamic one. In this process this sector is facing a number of challenges. In this changed context, the financial services industry in India has to play a very positive and dynamic role in the years to come by offering many innovative products to suit the varied requirements of the millions of prospective investors spread throughout the country. Reforms of the financial sector constitute the most important component of India's programme towards economic liberalization.

Growth in financial services (comprising banking, insurance, real estate and business services), after dipping to 5.6% in 2003-04 bounced back to 8.7% in 2004-05 and 10.9% in 2005-06. The momentum has been maintained with a growth of 11.1% in 2006-07. Because of Globalization, the financial services industry is in a period of transition. Market shifts, competition, and technological developments are ushering in unprecedented changes in the global financial services industry. But in the year 2011-12 the growth rate declined to 6.5%.

17.4. Impact on Export and Import:

India's Export and Import in the year 2001-02 was to the extent of 32,572 and 38,362 million respectively. Many Indian companies have started becoming respectable players in the International scene. Agriculture exports account for about 13 to 18% of total annual of annual export of the country. In 2000-01 Agricultural products valued at more than US \$ 6million were exported from the country 23% of which was contributed by the marine products alone. Marine products in recent years have emerged as the single largest contributor to the total agricultural export from the country accounting for over one fifth of the total agricultural exports. Cereals (mostly basmati rice and non-basmati rice), oil seeds, tea and coffee are the other prominent products each of which accounts fro nearly 5 to 10% of the country's total agricultural exports.

18.0 Advantages of Globalization:

- There is an International market for companies and for consumers there is a wider range of products to choose from.
- Increase in flow of investments from developed countries to developing countries, which can be used for economic reconstruction.
- Greater and faster flow of information between countries and greater cultural interaction has helped to overcome cultural barriers.
- Technological development has resulted in reverse brain drain in developing countries.

19. Demerits of Globalization (Challenges):

- The outsourcing of jobs to developing countries has resulted in loss of jobs in developed countries.
- There is a greater threat of spread of communicable diseases.
- There is an underlying threat of multinational corporations with immense power ruling the globe.
- For smaller developing nations at the receiving end, it could indirectly lead to a subtle form of colonization.
- The number of rural landless families increased from 35 %in 1987 to 45 % in 1999, further to 55% in 2005. The farmers are destined to die of starvation or suicide.

20. A Comparison with Other Developing Countries:

- Consider global trade – India’s share of world merchandise exports increased from .05% to .07% over the past 20 years. Over the same period China’s share has tripled to almost 4%.
- India’s share of global trade is similar to that of the Philippines an economy 6 times smaller according to IMF estimates.
- Over the past decade FDI flows into India have averaged around 0.5% of GDP against 5% for China and 5.5% for Brazil. FDI inflows to China now exceed US \$ 50 billion annually. It is only US \$ 4billion in the case of India.

21. Findings

The competitive intelligence practice can be significant. By setting ‘intelligent’ goals and by factoring ‘probability of success’ into their actions, competitive-intelligence, companies and their shareholders are rewarded with higher investment returns.

- A major research company closely monitors the progress of competitor’s projects to guide management of their own research investing. By measuring the progress of their own research projects against those of competitors they are able to quickly divert research investments from unproductive projects to research that is more probable to take the lead on competitors. Savings can amount to \$1Million/day/project.
- A national brand company was steadily losing market share to competitors and was confused about root causes. By closely monitoring competitor operations they were able to learn that their own operations had fallen behind and then make the changes to stem the loss of market share and become competitive again.
- A national information technology services company constantly monitors the business volumes, resources, financial health and stock prices of its close competitors. It grows in size, market coverage, and value through selective acquisitions of (former) competitors.
- A global tire manufacturer and a major automaker ignored the chat room information about failures of their products. They lost market share, their stock prices plummeted, and they are now settling a long string of lawsuits.

22. Limitations-Present research is conceptualized and based on secondary data; research could have been more authenticated if it would have been based on primary data.

21. Conclusion:

In practice, the intelligence product is unlikely to be created from perfect input. We cannot truly and accurately predict the future until events have already taken place and it's too late. The firm finds itself in a position where it can only react to the competitor's move; it has lost the advantage it might have had if the right intelligence had been available earlier. So, although we can't know for certain the minutiae associated with exact details, we can discover plans and roughly-hewn strategies.

CI's real value is to provide managers with the organizational tool to learn what the competitor will do, not what the competitor has already done.

Globalization, in a fundamental sense, is not a new phenomenon. Its roots extend farther and deeper than the visible part of the plant. It is as old as history, starting with the great migrations of people across the great landmasses. Only recent developments in computer and communication technologies have accelerated the process of integration, with geographic distances becoming less of a factor. Is this 'end of geography' a boon or a bane? Borders have become porous and the sky is open. Nothing is an unmixed blessing. Globalization in its present form though spurred by far reaching technological changes is not a pure technological phenomenon. It has many dimensions including ideological. To deal with this phenomenon, we must understand the gains and losses, the benefits as well as dangers. To be forewarned, as the saying goes, is to be forearmed. But we should not throw the baby with bath water. We should also resist the temptation to blame globalization for all our failures. Most often, as the poet said, the fault is in us.

Risks of an open economy are well known. We must not, nevertheless, miss the opportunities that the global system can offer. As an eminent critic put it, the world cannot marginalize India. But India, if it chooses, can marginalize itself. We must guard ourselves against this danger.

The key to India's growth lies in improving productivity and efficiency. This has to permeate all walks of our life. Contrary to the general impression, the natural resources of our country are not large. India accounts for 16.7 per cent of world's population whereas it has only 2.0 per cent of world's land area. While China's population is 30 per cent higher than that of

India's, it has a land area which is three times that of India. In fact, from the point of view of long-range sustainability, the need for greater efficiency in the management of natural resources like land, water and minerals has become urgent. In a capital-scarce economy like ours, efficient utilization of our capacity becomes even more critical.

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